





Overall, the results provide evidence that SA biosynthesis from MD could have a positive effect in the response of peach plants to PPV infection, reducing symptomatology. The MD pathway could then provide a good target for the development of transgenic plants resistant to PPV.

Project ID: 2015-E-147 Determine different *Plum pox virus* strains in wild hosts and in stone fruit cultivars with different susceptibility as a part of improved control and surveillance strategies

References:

Diaz-Vivancos P., Bernal-Vicente A., Cantabella D., Petri C., Hernández J.A (2017). Metabolomics and biochemical approaches link salicylic acid biosynthesis to cyanogenesis in peach plants. *Plant Cell Physiology* 58(12): 2057-2066. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pcp/pcx135>.